

PATIENT HISTORY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Background

The organization and Business Domain

Family Medical Center which is situated in the Gampaha district has a patient base of over 700, where they examine at least 80 - 120 patients a day. It has 2 doctors and five other employees working as the pharmacist, laboratory assistants, cashier and receptionist.

Current Situation of the System

Due to the increasing workload, they have already adopted a computerized system to manage the overall managerial functions of the organization. But there have been constant complains by the doctors that they have a problem in recollecting patient history because the system doesn't provide a proper facility for that. Currently the system only provides patient registration details and medical allergy related details only when it comes to patients. In addition, the system provides details about the medicine currently held in the pharmacy and laboratory reports to be collected and appointments.

System Analysis

Problem Statement

The system does not properly carry details of the patients' history related to all medical treatments specially conducted by the organization itself. Therefore, doctors find it hard and time consuming in recollecting the patients' history. They further point out that difficulty in finding out patient history causes accuracy problems and problems in providing the relevant treatments.

The Requirements

The Functional Requirements from the system are as follows:

- Registering patients to the system:
The patients would be given a card with a unique number or barcode in it which would be used as the main mode of identifying them and recording and accessing their details current, past and recording the future.
- Provision of a card to the patients with a unique number and barcode:
The card would be the main mode of assistance when recording and accessing the details of patients especially those related to their history.
- Recording and Updating Patient Details:
The doctor would be able to record the medicine prescribed, current changes in the health such as newly identified allergies especially helpful when recording the patient's health details and treating them.
- Prescribing medicine and sending the prescription to the pharmacy, receptionist and laboratory according to the requirement
Through this the main aim is to save the time of the patient and improve the productivity of the medical center at the same time where these would be sent to the relevant parties using a single click.
- Issuing medicine and laboratory reports
The laboratory and pharmacists would be mainly performing these tasks where these would be based on the prescription of the doctors. Further, the collection date of the reports would also can be notified and recorded in the system once stored in the system.
- Removing patient details
Once the patient dies or leaves the country, their details would be removed. Further modifications would be done to information based on the request of the doctors or patients.

The Non-Functional Requirements from the system are as follows.

- The card given to patients with the unique identification number and barcode.
- Modification of patient details.
- Rights of the receptionist, doctor, pharmacist and laboratory assistant
- Issuing appointments to patients

The Database Requirements of the system are as follows.

- Entering and holding patients' information:
Patients' personal identification details including the name, age, address, email address are entered by the receptionist. Patients' medicine and treatment i.e. health related information is entered by the doctors.
- Updating patients' information:
The personal identification details of patients would be updated mainly by the receptionist. Health and medical related information would be updated by the doctor. Each patient would be separately identified before updates are done through the unique barcode or number in the card.
- Searching information about patients
The system would overall have the following modules in it: Search, Channeling, Appointment, Patient, Users, Medicine and Medical Records

System Development

Notepad++ has been used in developing this web-based system. Furthermore, Patient History Management System has been developed mainly using HTML, CSS: Bootstrap, JavaScript and PHP. The framework Angular JS has also been used.

The database MySQL was considered as the database for this system to record patient history. WAMP server has been used with the database to

facilitate it based on the benefits of security, scalability, better performance, high availability, manageability and integration.

The interfaces have been developed using Notepad++ while maintaining the consistency, user familiarity, efficiency and effectiveness. Buttons and colours have been used to facilitate the ease of identification and understanding of the users.

Conclusion

Clearly stated the Family Medical Center has a system currently only to manage the administrative work and details when it comes to their patient history they are still using a manual process which has still caused a problem to them. Therefore, they are in need of such a system.

Achievements:

- Increase of efficiency through examining more patients a day.
- Increase of accuracy
- Reduced risk of unauthorized access to information through various access levels provided to each staff member based on the tasks they perform
- Efficient collection and recording of patient related details
- Saves the time taken to examine one patient through which more patients can be examined a day.
- Easy sharing of data and information within the center.

Future Enhancements

As the system is limited only to the doctors, pharmacist, receptionist and the laboratory assistant at the medical center, as future enhancements the main focus is to allow patients to book their appointments online through the same system rather than relying on the receptionist for the same purpose.

References

Piyush Jain, S. K. (2012) 'Analysis and Performance Evaluation of Software System Usability', *International Journal of Computer Applications.*, 43(17), pp.24-29.